

PRISMA-P Protocol - Systematic Review

Situational interest in physical education: a systematic review

OBEPIN_Studie_1

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ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

Title

Situational interest in physical education: a systematic review

1a. Identification:

This document is the protocol of a systematic review developed in accordance with the PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols) 2015 guidelines (Moher & al, 2015).

1b. Update:

This protocol is not an update of a previous review.

Registration

2. Registration:

The protocol is intended for registration in PROSPERO; a registration number will be added once assigned, and this dated protocol will be updated accordingly. As of this version, the record is not yet published in PROSPERO.

Authors

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3b. Contributions:

- Conceptualisation & methodology: SH (lead), GK, BC, OP
- Search strategy & piloting: SH (lead), GK, BC, OP
- Screening & data extraction: SH (lead), CLG, LF
- Risk of bias assessment: SH (lead), CLG, LF, GK, BC
- Synthesis & writing: SH (lead), BC, GK, OP
- Guarantor of the review: SH (responsible for scientific and methodological integrity).

Amendments

Amendments:

This protocol does not represent an amendment to a previously completed or published protocol.

This document constitutes Version 1 (V1) of the protocol. All stages prior to data extraction - including the conceptual rationale, eligibility criteria, information sources and search strategy, and study selection procedures - have been completed. Any future changes will be strictly limited to the phases of data extraction, use of tools, and data handling/processing. Should any such modifications be required, we will issue Version 2 (V2) of the protocol on Zenodo, accompanied by a dated change log that clearly describes the amendments made, the sections affected, and the rationale for each change.

Support

5a. Sources:

The review has no external funding and no agreed institutional support; it is conducted in the authors' own time.

5b. Sponsor:

None.

5c. Role of sponsor or funder:

Not applicable, as no sponsor/funder is involved.

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

6. Rationale:

Why this review is necessary ?

While SI is theoretically defined as a transient, environmentally triggered affective reaction, current literature presents two significant gaps. First, although various pedagogical and experimental interventions (e.g., gamification, autonomy support) are used to stimulate SI, there has been no comprehensive systematic synthesis of the specific effects of these interventions on the five dimensions of SI (novelty, challenge, attentional demand, intention exploration, and instant enjoyment) nor of their long-term effect. Second, a theoretical tension exists: while SI is theoretically independent of personal dispositions, empirical evidence regarding how individual characteristics - such as sex, weight status, or motor expertise - influence SI variations remain conflicting and fragmented.

What it adds to existing knowledge ?

This review will provide the first comprehensive synthesis to:

- (1) examine the relationships between students' individual characteristics and their SI variations, by assessing whether the associations reported in existing studies appear homogeneous (i.e., consistent) or heterogeneous (i.e., divergent) across the school population
- (2) examine the effects of pedagogical and experimental interventions in PE on students' SI, identifying the characteristics of the intervention that foster SI most effectively, the SI dimensions they affect, and the magnitude and durability of these effects.

By bridging these gaps, this review moves beyond isolated findings to offer a holistic understanding of the mechanisms that trigger and sustain SI.

Objectives

7. Objectives:

What individual characteristics of students are associated with variations in the expression of SI in PE?

- Which sociodemographic and individual characteristics of students (e.g., age, sex, grade level, weight status, and other personal dispositions) are associated with variations in SI in PE, and do these associations remain consistent across the population or differ across specific subgroups or contexts?
- Which psychological or dispositional characteristics of students (e.g., perceived competence, individual interest, motivational dispositions, and level of expertise) are associated with variations in SI in PE?

What effects do pedagogical and experimental interventions have on students' SI in PE ?

- Which characteristics of PE interventions (e.g., exergames, individual vs collective task formats, autonomy-supportive teaching, material variety, task difficulty and gamification) most effectively foster SI?
- Which dimensions of SI are affected, and to what extent?
- What are the short, medium and long-term effects of these interventions on students (e.g., interest dynamics, SI-IItransition, PA) ?

METHODS

Eligibility criteria

8. Eligibility criteria:

Study and report characteristics

Eligible studies are empirical investigations - quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods - conducted within curricular physical education (PE) lessons involving secondary school students aged 9-18 years. We included participants aged 9-18 because the starting age of secondary education varies internationally (from about 9 to 12 years depending on the system), while 18 is typically the upper age at which students complete secondary school. This range ensures

inclusion of all studies identified by authors as secondary PE and maintains developmental coherence for analysing SI. Both ecological PE lessons and controlled experimental tasks implemented in PE contexts are eligible. There are no date restrictions. Language is not restricted.

In addition, eligible articles must: (1) be peer-reviewed empirical research (not theoretical or non-scientific reports such as editorials, commentaries, or conference abstracts/proceedings); (2) be published in journals indexed in Web of Science (verification via the Master Journal List) or Scopus (verification via SCImago); and (3) include at least one operational measure of situational interest (SI) analysed as a primary outcome or a relevant secondary variable.

Exclusions comprise: theoretical papers without data, editorials, commentaries, conference abstracts/proceedings, studies conducted in extracurricular clubs or community programmes. Studies in which “SI” is only mentioned without being measured or analysed. Studies published in journals not indexed in Web of Science or Scopus are also excluded.

- **Population.** Secondary students aged 9-18 years enrolled in timetabled, compulsory school PE lessons, across any sex/background, any PE content, any country. Exclusions: university students or non-students; students practice an activities conducted in extracurricular sports, clubs, camps, community settings.
- **Interventions.** Pedagogical or experimental interventions conducted within PE contexts, in ecological lessons or controlled tasks relevant to PE learning. Exclusions: studies not involving a pedagogical or experimental intervention in a PE context.
- **Comparators.** Any comparator is acceptable; no exclusions are applied based on comparator
- **Outcomes.** Open to any outcome structure. situational interest (SI) in PE, both global and across five dimensions -novelty, challenge, attentional demand, exploration intention, and instant enjoyment - as assessed by validated instruments (e.g., SI Scale or equivalent), at any available time-point (during tasks, immediately post-activity, across lessons). Downstream outcomes (e.g., SI→II dynamics, engagement, PA intentions) will be extracted when reported

Information sources

9. Information sources:

Searches were conducted in PsycInfo and Scopus (primary databases), and in ERIC, SPORTDiscus, PubPsych, Cairn, and ScienceDirect (supplementary discipline/coverage databases). In addition, we implemented backward and forward citation chasing (via Citation Chaser) and screened the reference lists of included studies, with targeted scoping in Google Scholar to minimise retrieval bias. No date limits were applied. Database-specific field tags and filters were used where appropriate to each platform - while preserving a uniform conceptual strategy across sources.

Search strategy

10. Search strategy:

A comprehensive and reproducible search strategy was developed by identifying the core conceptual domains underpinning the review - physical education, the target student population, and situational interest - and selecting keywords directly derived from the research questions and the theoretical framework guiding the review. The choice of search terms was informed by the terminology recurrently used in foundational SI literature, by descriptors appearing in empirical studies grounded in this framework, and by vocabulary specific to the PE context in both English and French. The resulting Boolean structure therefore integrated conceptual, methodological, and disciplinary relevance. The final search string combined an extensive set of keywords covering: (1) the PE context (e.g., Éducation physique, EPS, PE, Physical education), (2) the target population of school-aged learners (e.g., élèves, students, adolescents, secondary school, pupils), and (3) the focal construct of situational interest (e.g., situational interest, intérêt en situation, intérêt, individual interest). This strategy was applied consistently across databases to ensure broad coverage, conceptual sensitivity, and full reproducibility.

Key words and boolean queries : (Éducation physique et sportive OR Éducation physique OR EPS OR PE OR Physical education) AND (Student OR students OR Students' OR Childhood OR Adolescent OR adolescents OR adolescentes OR élève OR élèves OR secondary school OR middle school OR pupils OR early-adolescents OR Children) AND (Situational interest OR intérêt en situation OR intérêt OR interest OR intérêt individuel OR individual interest OR profils d'intérêt)

PsycInfo

éducation physique et sportive OU EPS OU physical education OU PE OU éducation physique ET situational interest OU intérêt en situation OU intérêt individuel OU individual interest

- With the « langage commun » filter

PubPsych

("éducation physique et sportive" OR "EPS" OR "physical education" OR "PE" OR "éducation physique") AND ("situational interest" OR "intérêt en situation" OR "intérêt individuel" OR "individual interest")

- With no filter.

Eric

(title:("éducation physique et sportive" OR "éducation physique" OR "EPS" OR "PE" OR "physical education") OR abstract:("éducation physique et sportive" OR "éducation physique" OR "EPS" OR "PE" OR "physical education")) AND (title:("student" OR "students" OR "students'" OR "childhood" OR "adolescent" OR "adolescents" OR "adolescents'" OR "adolescentes" OR "élève" OR "élèves" OR "secondary school" OR "primary school" OR "middle school" OR "école primaire" OR "pupils" OR "early-adolescents" OR "children") OR abstract:("student" OR "students" OR "students'" OR "childhood" OR "adolescent" OR "adolescents" OR "adolescents'" OR "adolescentes" OR "élève" OR "élèves" OR "secondary school" OR "primary school" OR "middle school" OR "école primaire" OR "pupils" OR "early-adolescents" OR "children")) AND (title:("situational interest" OR "intérêt en situation" OR "intérêt individuel" OR "individual interest" OR "profils d'intérêt") OR

abstract:("situational interest" OR "intérêt en situation" OR "intérêt individuel" OR "individual interest" OR "profils d'intérêt"))

- With no filter.

Scopus

TITLE-ABS-KEY("éducation physique et sportive" OR "éducation physique" OR "EPS" OR "PE" OR "physical education") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("situational interest" OR "intérêt en situation" OR "intérêt individuel" OR "individual interest" OR "profils d'intérêt")

- With no filter.

SportDiscuss

("éducation physique et sportive" OR "éducation physique" OR "EPS" OR "PE" OR "physical education") AND ("student" OR "students" OR "students'" OR "childhood" OR "adolescent" OR "adolescents" OR "adolescents'" OR "adolescentes" OR "élève" OR "élèves" OR "secondary school" OR "primary school" OR "middle school" OR "école primaire" OR "pupils" OR "early-adolescents" OR "children") AND ("situational interest" OR "intérêt en situation" OR "intérêt individuel" OR "individual interest" OR "profils d'intérêt")

- With no filter

Cairn

éducation physique et sportive OU EPS OU physical education OU PE OU éducation physique ET situational interest OU intérêt en situation OU intérêt individuel OU individual interest

- With the « revues » filter.

Sciencesdirect

("éducation physique et sportive" OR "EPS" OR "physical education" OR "PE" OR "éducation physique") AND ("situational interest" OR "intérêt en situation" OR "intérêt individuel" OR "individual interest")

- With the « review articles » and « research articles » filters.

Google Scholar

A manual research have been done alternating the main keywords and boolean queries.

Citation Chaser

Following completion of the primary title/abstract and full-text screening phases, we conducted both backward and forward citation chasing using Citation Chaser on the set of studies that had been finally included. All records retrieved through citation chasing were exported and merged with the initial corpus, after which we re-ran the entire study-identification workflow

Study records

11a. Data management:

All results retrieved from each database were exported in bulk as RIS files and imported directly into Rayyan for centralised record management and duplicate detection. For sources that did not support bulk RIS export, individual records were first added to a dedicated Zotero library; once the library was complete, it was exported as a single RIS file and then imported into Rayyan.

11b. Selection process:

All records from the database searches and supplementary sources were imported into Rayyan, where duplicate records were first detected algorithmically and then verified manually before screening proceeded by two independent reviewers.

Title/abstract screening was conducted independently, in duplicate, with reviewers blinded to each other's decisions. Disagreements were resolved by consensus. This double-review approach was also applied to any updates of the protocol and search sets. Rayyan's decision-support features were used to assist (but not replace) human judgement throughout the process.

For records retained at this stage, full texts were retrieved and assessed independently in duplicate, under blinded conditions, with reasons for exclusion recorded at the full-text stage to enable transparent reporting in the PRISMA flow. Any persisting disagreements were adjudicated by a third reviewer.

11c. Data collection process:

Data collection will be conducted only for studies included after full-text screening, as described in the selection process (11b). Two reviewers will independently collect data using a structured and standardized data-collection form specifically developed for this review. Before full implementation, the form will be piloted on a small subset of included studies to ensure clarity, consistency across reviewers, and alignment with the review objectives. Any modifications made following piloting will be documented.

Each reviewer will complete the data collection independently and in parallel. Extracted information will then be compared, and discrepancies will be resolved through discussion. When agreement cannot be reached, a third reviewer will adjudicate. All decisions and their rationale will be recorded to maintain transparency and reproducibility.

When essential information is missing, unclear, or insufficiently reported in the original publication, the review team will contact the study authors via email to request clarification or supplementary data. Authors will be given two weeks to respond. If no reply is received, a single reminder will be sent. In the absence of a response after this second attempt, the corresponding information will be classified as missing data and treated accordingly during synthesis.

All versions of the data-collection form, duplicate extraction files, adjudication notes, and logs of author correspondence will be stored securely to ensure full traceability of the data-collection process. Any machine-assisted tools used to support the process will be manually verified by the reviewers before inclusion.

Data items

12. Data items:

Data will be extracted on all variables necessary to describe the included studies, characterize participants and PE interventions, document instruments and analyses, and address the review objectives. Categories, variable names, coding formats, and rules for handling multiple groups/follow-ups are specified below, in accordance with PRISMA-P Item 12.

1) Primary Study Information : Summary of Included Studies

- **StudyRef** - Study reference (open text). Rule: last name of first author + publication year; if a study reports multiple samples, append a single letter (e.g., Kermarrec2016a).
- **Title** - Article title (open text).
- **Country** - Country where the study took place (open text).
- **Type of research & methods of collection** - Research type and data-collection methods (e.g., quantitative, qualitative, mixed methods; questionnaires, sensors, observations) (open text).
- **Publication language** - Publication language (open text).
- **Purpose** - Study aim/purpose (open text).
- **Results** - Brief summary of key findings as reported (open text).

2) Study Characteristics

- **Design** - Study design: between-subject / within-subject.
- **DesignDetail** - Design details/precision (e.g., randomization, counterbalancing, task structure) (open text).
- **TotSize** - Total sample size (integer ≥ 1).
- **SampleSize** - Intervention group size (integer ≥ 1). Multiple intervention groups: add SampleSize2, SampleSize3, etc.
- **CompSize** - Comparator group size (integer ≥ 1).
- **Gpe** - Number of groups (integer ≥ 1).
- **FollUp** - Post-intervention follow-up: 0 = no; 1 = yes.
- **FUp** - Follow-up timing in weeks (integer ≥ 0). Same-day follow-up \rightarrow code 0. Multiple follow-ups: add FUp2, FUp3, etc.
- **SampleSizeFUp** — Intervention group size at follow-up (integer ≥ 1).
- **Comp** - Comparator type: 0 = control; 1 = waitlist; 2 = exercise; 3 = other activity.
- **PreReg** - Study protocol pre-registered: 0 = no; 1 = yes.
- **PsychTh** - Psychological theory used in the intervention (open text; e.g., Situational Interest theory).
- **DelPer** - Individual delivering the sport/PE program: 0 = researcher; 1 = PE teacher; 2 = PA professional (e.g., coach).
- **CompSizeFUp** - Comparator group size at follow-up (integer ≥ 1).

3) Sample characteristics

- **Age** - Mean age (years; numeric ≥ 0 ; decimals allowed).

- **Sex** - Percentage of females recorded as a proportion in [0,1] (e.g., 0.40 for 40%).
- **SchoolLevel** - School level (open text; e.g., lower secondary school students).
- **Eth** - Primary ethnicity (open text).
- **BMI** - Body Mass Index (kg/m²; numeric ≥ 0).
- **Diseases** - Type of disease (open text).
- **PopOtherSpecificity** - Other dispositional/psychological specificities (open text).

4) PE Intervention characteristics

- **IC_ContInt** - Intervention context: 0 = out of PE lesson; 1 = PE lesson.
- **IC_Target** - Intervention directly designed to alter SI: 0 = no; 1 = yes.
- **IC_InstructorCharacteristics** - Instructor characteristics (open text; e.g., expert).
- **IC_PAType** - Physical activity type (open text; e.g., badminton).
- **IC_AVG-NumTools** - Active video games / numeric tools (open text; e.g., AVG).
- **IC_DurMin** - Duration in minutes (integer ≥ 1).
- **IC_Intensity** - Exercise intensity: 0 = Moderate; 1 = Vigorous.
- **IC_Teaching style** - Teaching style (open text; e.g., supportive).
- **IC_InstructionalContent** - Instructional content (open text).
- **IC_SI_DimTargeted** - SI dimension(s) targeted (open text; e.g., Novelty).
- **IC_SocialCharacteristics** - Social characteristics/organization (open text; e.g., Dyad).
- **IC_ChoiceOpportunities** - Choice opportunities (open text; e.g., Yes + details).
- **IC_FeedBack** - Feedback (open text; e.g., video feedback).
- **IC_Challenge** - Challenge (open text).
- **IC_Novelty** - Novelty (open text).
- **IC_Other** - Other characteristics (open text).

5) Measurement instruments

- **MI_Name** - Measurement instrument name (open text; e.g., EMIS-EP).
- **MI_Type** - Measurement instrument type (open text; e.g., psychometric questionar).
- **MI_Validated** - Reported validation: 0 = no; 1 = yes.
- **MI_Group** - Measurement group identifier (integer ≥ 1).

6) Data analyses

- **Stats1, Stats2, Stats3** - Statistical techniques employed for analysis (open text; e.g., ANOVA, mixed models, correlations).

7) Study Results: Situational Interest (primary) and others (secondary)

A. Impact of intervention on SI

- **SI_Total_Effect** - Effect on Total SI: Yes/No.
- **Time_Measurement** - Number of repeated measurements (integer ≥ 1).
- **CG/EG_Effect** - Between-group effects (comparator vs. intervention): Yes/No.
- **Within_Effect** - Within-subject effects: Yes/No.
- **InterventionCharacteristics** - Main characteristics of the intervention (open text).

- **SI_OtherDimensions_Effect** - Effect on other SI dimensions (open text; specify which).
- **S-M-L_Term_Effect** - Short/Medium/Long-term effect (open text).

B. Association_SI_II

- **Asso_SI_II** - Association between Individual Interest (II) and SI: Yes/No.
- **IS_Dimensions** - Which SI dimensions were stimulated with II (open text).
- **II_Dimensions** - Which II dimensions were stimulated with SI (open text).

C. Association_SI_SubjectSocioDemoCaracteristics

- **Association_SI_SubjectSocioDemoCaracteristics** - Association between socio-demographic characteristics and SI: Yes/No.
- **SubjectSocioDemoCaracteristics** - Which characteristics (e.g., age, sex) (open text).
- **IS_Dimensions** - Which SI dimensions were associated (open text).

D. Association_SI_PsychoCaractSubject

- **Association_SI_PsychoCaractSubject** - Association between psychometric characteristics and SI: Yes/No.
- **PsychoCaractSubject** - Which psychometric dimensions (e.g., motivation, perceived competence) (open text).
- **IS_Dimensions** - Which SI dimensions were associated (open text).

E. Association_SI_MVPA

- **Association_SI_MVPA** - Association between PA and SI: Yes/No.
- **MVPA** - Which MVPA (e.g., vigorous) (open text).
- **IS_Dimensions** - Which SI dimensions were associated (open text).

8) Funding and Competing Interests

- **FundingSource** - Funding source reported: Yes/No.
- **ConflictOfInterest** - Conflict of interest reported: Yes/No.

9) Quality Assessment (tool by design type)

- **QQM** - All included studies, any design: record the percentage score (0–100%) from the Quality appraisal tool for quantitative/qualitative/mixed-methods studies.
- **ROBIN-I V2** - Non-randomized intervention studies: record the overall risk of bias (verbatim as reported using ROBIN-I V2).
- **ROB2** - Randomized trials: record the overall risk of bias per the Cochrane ROB 2 framework (verbatim as reported). (This split preserves a cross-design quality view with QQM while adding design-specific internal-validity appraisals for NRCTs and RCTs.)

10) Overall certainty of evidence

- **GRADE-CERQual** — Overall certainty/confidence for qualitative evidence.
- **GRADE** — Overall certainty for quantitative evidence.

11) Missing data and author contacts

- Information judged missing or unclear will be noted.
- Details of any data requested from authors will be documented.

Outcomes and prioritization

13. Outcomes and prioritization:

Primary outcome

(A) Situational interest (SI) in PE, analysed both as a global construct and across its five dimensions (novelty, challenge, attentional demand, exploration intention, instant enjoyment), at any reported time-point, measured with validated instruments. (B) Associations between student characteristics (e.g., age, sex, grade, weight status, perceived competence, expertise, motivational dispositions, II) and variations in SI. (C) effects of pedagogical/experimental interventions on SI and its dimensions

Secondary outcomes

Downstream indicators such as interest dynamics (SI→II), engagement, motivation, and physical activity intentions/doses, when reported. Prioritisation follows the review's two foci: student profiles and interventions.

Risk of bias in individual studies

14. Risk of bias in individual studies:

Quality appraisal was conducted using a two-layered and design-sensitive approach.

First, all included studies, regardless of design, were assessed using the Quality appraisal tool for Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed-Methods studies (QQM). The QQM provides a cross-design, overarching assessment of study quality, encompassing multiple dimensions beyond risk of bias alone, including internal validity, external validity, precision, reporting quality, and applicability. This global quality judgement allowed a standardized comparison of methodological quality across heterogeneous study designs. All QQM assessments were performed independently by two reviewers under blinded conditions, with discrepancies resolved through consensus or, when necessary, adjudication by a third reviewer.

Second, design-specific risk-of-bias tools were applied to provide a more granular evaluation of internal validity:

- For non-randomised intervention studies (NRCTs), risk of bias was assessed using the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Interventions (ROBINS-I), Version 2, following the tool's structured domain-based framework and overall risk-of-bias judgement.
- For randomised controlled trials (RCTs), risk of bias was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized trials (ROB 2), allowing evaluation of bias arising from the

randomization process, deviations from intended interventions, missing outcome data, outcome measurement, and selective reporting.

Both ROBINS-I (V2) and ROB 2 assessments were conducted independently in duplicate, with disagreements resolved by consensus or third-reviewer adjudication. Risk-of-bias judgements were reported alongside the QQM global quality score, thereby preserving both a design-specific internal validity assessment and a broader, cross-design appraisal of overall study quality.

Data synthesis

15a. Criteria under which study data will be quantitatively synthesised:

We will not perform a meta-analysis. Instead, we will conduct a structured narrative synthesis following the SWiM reporting guideline and the Cochrane Handbook (Chapter 12) for reviews that do not pool effect estimates.

Quantitative summaries without pooling. Where appropriate, we will report simple quantitative descriptors to aid interpretation - e.g., number of studies, group sizes (intervention/comparator), number of measurement time points, and basic descriptive statistics (means/SDs or medians/IQRs) - and we will standardize effect direction for comparability (higher = greater SI). Any transformation to a common display metric (e.g., SMD) will be for presentation only and not pooled.

We will avoid vote-counting by p-values and may use effect-direction or harvest plots and structured tables to summarize patterns across pre-specified groups (e.g., intervention characteristics, context, outcomes/instruments). Interpretation will be made in light of study quality/risk of bias.

15b. Summary measures, data handling, methods of combining studies and exploration of consistency:

No effect estimates will be pooled. Summary information will be presented descriptively (study/group counts, group sizes, time points, means/SDs or medians/IQRs). For interpretability, we will standardize effect direction and, when necessary, present unpooled standardized metrics (e.g., SMD) solely to enable like-for-like visual comparison. We will explore consistency narratively across pre-specified groupings (design, context, intervention features, measurement instrument/timing), using structured tabulation and non-pooled visualizations (effect-direction/harvest plots), explicitly eschewing vote-counting by significance.

15c. Proposed additional analyses:

No subgroup meta analyses are planned. We will undertake pre specified, design sensitive narrative comparisons by:

- Student characteristics (e.g., age, sex, school level/grade, weight status/BMI, perceived competence, expertise, individual interest).
- Intervention characteristics (e.g., context, duration/intensity, PA type, SI dimension targeted, teaching style, feedback, choice, social organisation, use of active video games/tech).

We will investigate heterogeneity narratively across these groups (e.g., differences in direction/size patterns) and conduct risk of bias aware sensitivity interpretations (considering

QQM, ROBINS I V2 for non randomized studies, and ROB2 for randomized trials). Where relevant, we will specify prioritization criteria (e.g., lower risk of bias, directness to the review question) when summarizing key messages, in line with SWiM items on grouping, synthesis methods, heterogeneity, and prioritization.

15d. Summary approach if quantitative synthesis is not appropriate:

A structured narrative synthesis will be conducted following the SWiM reporting guideline. We will:

- Group studies transparently (and justify any changes from the protocol).
- Specify the standardized metric/direction used for presentation and document any transformations.
- Describe the synthesis method (structured tables; non-pooled visualizations such as effect-direction/harvest plots; optional forest-style displays without pooling).
- Present results as evidence maps/thematic tables, stating which studies contribute to each finding and how data are ordered (e.g., by design, instrument, or risk of bias).
- Summarize findings and their certainty/limitations, including limitations of the synthesis itself.
- These steps operationalize SWiM's nine reporting items and align with Cochrane guidance for synthesis without meta-analysis.

Meta-biases

16. Meta-biases:

Because no meta analysis is planned, we will not use funnel plots or small study tests. Potential reporting biases will be assessed qualitatively and reported transparently, consistent with the Cochrane Handbook guidance for syntheses without meta analysis and for missing results, and with selected SWiM reporting items.

- Within studies. We will flag signals of selective reporting by cross checking any available registrations/protocols against reported outcomes/time points (e.g., SI dimensions stated but not reported; omitted follow ups). These checks will be documented in the evidence tables.
- Across studies. We will qualitatively examine patterns compatible with publication/outcome reporting bias (e.g., recurrent non reporting of specific SI subscales or follow ups; systematic differences in effect direction by study size/precision—interpreted cautiously, not as hypothesis tests), presenting findings in structured tables and, where helpful, non pooled visualisations (effect direction/harvest plots).

Any implications of suspected reporting bias for certainty will be reflected in Item 17.

Confidence in cumulative evidence

17. Confidence in cumulative evidence:

Overall certainty will be appraised with GRADE for quantitative evidence and GRADE-CERQual for qualitative syntheses. Each synthesis statement will carry a rating - high, moderate, low, or very low - with a brief explicit justification and clear links to contributing studies.

- GRADE (quantitative). Judgements will consider the standard domains - risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, publication bias - applied to non-pooled bodies of evidence in line with the Cochrane Handbook; results will be summarised in text/tables (no statistical pooling).
- CERQual (qualitative). Judgements will consider methodological limitations, coherence, adequacy, and relevance for each qualitative finding, following the Cochrane-Campbell guidance.
- Transparency (SWiM-aligned). For each conclusion, we will indicate which studies contribute, how studies were grouped, and any limitations of the synthesis that affect certainty, consistent with SWiM's emphasis on clear reporting in reviews without meta-analysis.

REFERENCES

PRISMA-P Checklist

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QQM

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